

An Assessment of the Effects of COVID-19 and Modes of Data Collection on Selected NSDUH Estimates

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Abstract

The National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH) provides estimates of substance use and mental health among the civilian, noninstitutionalized population aged 12 or older in the United States. Until Quarter 1, 2020, data were collected via in-person interviewing. In 2020, due to the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, no data were collected in Quarter 2, and a limited number of interviews were conducted in Quarter 3. Multimode data collection (in person and via the web) was introduced in Quarter 4 of 2020 and continues to be used for NSDUH. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was not possible to conduct in advance a controlled experiment analyzing the effects of adding a web data collection mode on estimates. Thus, any potential effects of data collection mode and COVID-19 on estimates are not fully known. Therefore, to assess the effects of data collection mode and COVID-19 on estimates, log-binomial regression models were subsequently fit in SUDAAN[®], and three separate relative risks were calculated by comparing estimates from Quarter 1 in-person data, Quarters 3 and 4 in-person data, and Quarter 4 web data. For a set of key substance use and mental health outcomes, the data collection mode and COVID-19 effects were generally in the same direction (i.e., relative risks were either greater or less than 1 for both effects).

Key Words: Mode effects (in-person vs. web-based), National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH), COVID-19, relative risks, SUDAAN, log-binomial regression models

1. Introduction

The National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH) is an ongoing survey of the civilian, noninstitutionalized population aged 12 or older in the United States. Data are collected from January to December each year in all 50 states and the District of Columbia. NSDUH provides national, state, and substate data on substance use and mental health measures and the receipt of treatment services for these disorders in the United States. Approximately 67,500 interviews are completed annually.

Until Quarter 1, 2020, data were collected via face-to-face (in-person) interviewing. Quarter 1, 2020, data collection started with face-to-face interviewing, but because of the quickly spreading coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, data collection was suspended on March 16, 2020, and no data were collected in Quarter 2 of 2020. A small-scale in-person data collection effort was conducted in July 2020 to test protocols to reduce the risk of COVID-19 infection. Due to ongoing high COVID-19 infection rates in the United States, it became evident that a return to full-scale face-to-face data collection would not be feasible for obtaining a representative sample with a sufficient number of interviews to produce reliable national estimates with acceptable precision. Hence, a newly developed web data collection mode was utilized on October 30, 2020, to collect the NSDUH data for the remainder of the year. Face-to-face interviewing also resumed on October

1, 2020, in locations where COVID-19 infection metrics were sufficiently low (Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality, 2021). The face-to-face data collection method yielded $n=15,628$ respondents in Quarter 1, $n=42$ respondents in Quarter 3, and $n=1,412$ respondents in Quarter 4, whereas the web-based data collection method yielded $n=19,202$ respondents in Quarter 4. For these analyses, Quarter 3 face-to-face data were combined with Quarter 4 face-to-face data and henceforth treated as Quarter 4 face-to-face data.

Ideally, before changing the data collection mode in an ongoing survey, it is recommended to conduct a controlled experiment involving alternative data collection methods and existing data collection methods to evaluate any effect the data collection mode has on survey outcomes. Testing of web-based data collection for NSDUH in a controlled experiment was not possible due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, any effect of web-based data collection on 2020 NSDUH outcomes is not known. Additionally, the detrimental effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental, physical, and socioeconomic well-being of the general population may have affected the Quarter 4, 2020, NSDUH data. As a result, Quarter 1, 2020, data collected before the COVID-19 pandemic using face-to-face interviewing could be fundamentally different than Quarter 4, 2020, data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic using web-based data collection. Prior analyses assessing temporal effects on NSDUH outcomes using 2019 and earlier NSDUH data were inconclusive. Those temporal effects are treated as negligible here.

In the absence of any controlled experiment evaluating the effect of change in data collection mode and the confounding effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on NSDUH outcomes, it is difficult to fully disentangle and quantify factors affecting the Quarter 4, 2020, NSDUH data. In an effort to do so, several analyses were conducted and are described in this paper. Section 2 describes the 2020 NSDUH data and assumptions made in modeling the effects of COVID-19 and data collection mode on NSDUH outcomes. Section 3 describes the details of the fitted models, and Section 4 discusses the results.

2. Data and Assumptions

The 2020 NSDUH data were partitioned into the following three groups:

- G1: Quarter 1 face-to-face data collected before the COVID-19 pandemic,
- G2: Quarter 4 face-to-face data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic, and
- G3: Quarter 4 web-based data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Several key binary (1/0) substance use and mental health outcomes (Table 1), were analyzed to estimate the effects of data collection mode and COVID-19 on NSDUH estimates. Unweighted analyses were also performed for comparison purposes. However, only weighted results are presented.

To measure an average effect of COVID-19 on the prevalence of outcomes, a COVID variable was created and used in the modeling as described below:

COVID (C)=1 for all respondents in G2 and G3 and
=0 for all respondents in G1.

Additionally, to evaluate an average effect of data collection mode on the prevalence of outcomes, a MODE variable was created for the 2020 data and used in the modeling as described below:

MODE (M)=1 (face-to-face) for all respondents in G1 and G2 and
=0 (web) for all respondents in G3.

In order to compare estimates based on G1 data (face-to-face data collected before the COVID-19 pandemic) with estimates based on G3 data (web-based data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic), variable Q was created as described below:

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= 1 \text{ for all respondents in G1 and} \\ &= 0 \text{ for all respondents in G3.} \end{aligned}$$

Note that $Q=1$ is equivalent to $M=1, C=0$, and $Q=0$ is equivalent to $M=0, C=1$.

3. Methods

The analyses were conducted by fitting log-binomial regression models using LOGLINK regression procedure in SUDAAN[®] (RTI International, 2012). The LOGLINK procedure produces risk ratios (relative risks), as defined below, which are used in quantifying the effect of COVID-19 using the G1 and G2 data, effect of data collection mode using the G2 and G3 data, and combined effects of COVID-19 and data collection mode using the G1 and G3 data. The common categorical predictor variables in all models were age,¹ gender,² race/ethnicity,³ education,⁴ employment status,⁵ and county type.⁶ These predictors are available for the 2020 NSDUH data and are denoted by X in the following log-binomial regression models. The outcome variables, which are binary (0/1) variables, are denoted by Y , α 's are the regression coefficients corresponding to the predictor variable X , β_0 is the intercept, and β_C, β_M , and β_Q are the regression coefficients corresponding to predictor variables C, M , and Q , respectively.

Model 1: Estimation of risk ratio of COVID effect ($C=1$ vs. $C=0$)

To estimate the risk ratio of COVID effect, G1 and G2 data were used to fit the following model. Note that for G1 data, $M=1, C=0$, and for G2 data, $M=1, C=1$.

$$\log[P(Y = 1 | C, X)] = \beta_0 + \beta_C C + X_1 \alpha_1 + \dots + X_m \alpha_m \quad (1)$$

Using the above model, the risk ratio of COVID effect ($C=1$ vs. $C=0$) is

$$\frac{P(Y = 1 | C = 1, X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)}{P(Y = 1 | C = 0, X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)} = e^{\beta_C} = R_C, \quad (1a)$$

where x_1, \dots, x_m are given values of X s. Estimated R_C values are shown in Table 1.

Using the estimated value of R_C , for example, $R_C = 1.44$ (see Table 1), if Y denotes past month marijuana use, and x_1, \dots, x_m are the given set of predictor values, then one can infer that on average respondents in G2 (Quarter 4, face-to-face data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic) reported 44 percent more past month marijuana use than respondents in G1 (Quarter 1, face-to-face data collected before the COVID-19 pandemic).

¹ Age: 12-17, 18-25, 26-34, 35 or older

² Gender: Male, Female

³ Race/Ethnicity: Non-Hispanic White, Non-Hispanic Black, Non-Hispanic Other, Hispanic

⁴ Education: Less than High School, High School Graduate, Some College, College Graduate

⁵ Employment Status: Full Time, Part Time, Unemployed, Other

⁶ County Type: Large Metro, Small Metro, Nonmetro

Model 2: Estimation of risk ratio of MODE effect ($M=1$ vs. $M=0$)

To estimate the risk ratio of MODE effect, G2 and G3 data were used to fit the following model. Note that for G2 data, $M=1$, $C=1$, and for G3 data, $M=0$, $C=1$.

$$\log[P(Y = 1 | M, X)] = \beta_0 + \beta_M M + X_1 \alpha_1 + \dots + X_m \alpha_m \quad (2)$$

Using the above model, the risk ratio of MODE effect ($M=1$ vs. $M=0$) is

$$\frac{P(Y = 1 | M = 1, X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)}{P(Y = 1 | M = 0, X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)} = e^{\beta_M} = R_M, \quad (2a)$$

where x_1, \dots, x_m are given values of X s. Estimated R_M values are shown in Table 1.

Using the estimated value of R_M , for example, $R_M = 1.33$ (Table 1), if Y denotes past month marijuana use, and x_1, \dots, x_m are the given set of predictor values, then one can infer that on average face-to-face respondents in G2 (Quarter 4, face-to-face data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic) reported 33 percent more past month marijuana use than web respondents in G3 (Quarter 4, web-based data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic).

Model 3: Estimation of risk ratio of combined MODE and COVID-19 effects ($Q=1$ vs. $Q=0$)

To estimate the risk ratio of combined COVID and MODE effects, G1 and G3 data were used to fit the following model. Recall that for G1 data, $M=1$, $C=0$, and for G3 data, $M=0$, $C=1$, and testing of $Q=1$ vs. $Q=0$ is equivalent to testing $M=1$, $C=0$ vs. $M=0$, $C=1$.

$$\log[P(Y = 1 | Q, X)] = \beta_0 + \beta_Q Q + X_1 \alpha_1 + \dots + X_m \alpha_m \quad (3)$$

Using the above model, the risk ratio of $Q=1$ vs. $Q=0$ (i.e., $M=1$, $C=0$ vs. $M=0$, $C=1$) is

$$\frac{P(Y = 1 | Q = 1, X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)}{P(Y = 1 | Q = 0, X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)} = e^{\beta_Q} = R_Q, \quad (3a)$$

where x_1, \dots, x_m are given values of X s. Estimated R_Q values are shown in Table 1.

Noting that numerators of R_M and R_C are the same and dividing equation (2a) by equation (1a),

$$R_Q = \frac{R_M}{R_C}. \text{ This result is evident from Table 1, except for the cases where missing values in}$$

outcomes and predictor variables can create slight distortions. Also, noting that

$$\frac{P(Y = 1 | G1(M = 1, C = 0), X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)}{P(Y = 1 | G3(M = 0, C = 1), X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m)} = R_Q = \frac{R_M}{R_C},$$

$$P[Y = 1 | G1(M = 1, C = 0), X = x] = \frac{R_M}{R_C} P[Y = 1 | G3(M = 0, C = 1), X = x],$$

where $X = x$ denotes $[X_1 = x_1, \dots, X_m = x_m]$. If R_M and R_C are close to each other, then the overall effects of COVID and MODE cancel each other, resulting in about the same estimated probabilities using the data from the G1 and G3 groups, that is,

$$P[Y = 1 | G1(M = 1, C = 0), X = x] \approx P[Y = 1 | G3(M = 0, C = 1), X = x].$$

This is evident in several cases shown in Table 1 and is a notable finding. For example, the risk ratio of combined COVID and MODE effects for past year illicit drug use is $R_Q = 0.99$ and is not significant at the 5 percent level. This means that estimates of past year illicit drug use based on G1 data are not significantly different than estimates based on G3 data. This is because corresponding effects of COVID ($R_C = 1.28$) and MODE ($R_M = 1.25$) cancel each other, resulting in a nonsignificant difference between estimates. Note that $R_M = 1.25$ implies that on average respondents in G2 are 25 percent more likely to report past year illicit drug use than respondents in G3, and $R_C = 1.28$ implies that on average respondents in G2 interviewed during the COVID-19 pandemic are 28 percent more likely to report past year illicit drug use than respondents in G1 interviewed before the COVID-19 pandemic.

4. Discussion

The risk ratios obtained from Models 1, 2, and 3 are shown in Table 1. The first column lists selected NSDUH outcome measures, the second column lists risk ratios for MODE effect (face-to-face versus web), the third column lists risk ratios for COVID effect (during the COVID-19 pandemic versus before the COVID-19 pandemic), and the fourth column lists risk ratios for combined MODE-COVID effect (face-to-face before the COVID-19 pandemic versus web during the COVID-19 pandemic). The risk ratios significant at the 5 percent level are shown in boldface. The results presented assumed a negligible temporal effect on the estimates.

For example, the risk ratio for MODE effect for past year illicit drug use is 1.25, which is significant at the 5 percent level, and means that on average face-to-face respondents are 25 percent more likely to report past year illicit drug use than web respondents. Similarly, the corresponding risk ratio for COVID effect is 1.28 (also significant at the 5 percent level) and means that on average respondents during the COVID-19 pandemic reported 28 percent more past year illicit drug use than respondents before the COVID-19 pandemic. Because risk ratios for MODE and COVID effects are close to each other, the corresponding risk ratio for combined MODE-COVID effect in the fourth column is close to 1 and is not significant, implying that respondents in Quarter 1 reported about the same past year illicit drug use as web respondents in Quarter 4. In general, if risk ratios for MODE and COVID effects are close to each other (whether significant or not), then the corresponding combined risk ratio of MODE-COVID effect (R_Q) is close to 1 and may not be significant. It is possible for risk ratios for MODE and COVID effects to not be significant while the combined risk ratio for MODE-COVID effect is significant. This can be seen from the risk ratios for past month binge alcohol use (Table 1).

The effects for MODE and COVID increased as the reporting period changed from lifetime (not shown) to past year to past month use for the illicit drug, marijuana, and cigarette outcomes, with past month use showing the highest effects for MODE and COVID. In almost all cases, the effects for MODE and COVID were in the same direction (i.e., both are greater than 1 or both are less than 1 whether significant or not).

Having limited availability of face-to-face interview data in Quarter 4 of 2020 allowed risk ratios of effects of COVID-19 and data collection mode to be calculated. However, caution should be exercised in drawing conclusions from these results because of the limited number (n=1,454) of face-to-face interviews in Quarter 4 of 2020. Throughout 2021, effects of the COVID-19 pandemic

on substance use and mental health outcomes remained confounded with data collection mode because the local severity of the COVID-19 pandemic partially determined the availability of face-to-face interview data collection. Because of the addition of web-based data collection mode in 2020, which resulted in significant differences between face-to-face and web-based data, and two quarters of missing data in 2020, SAMHSA decided not to compare 2020 estimates with those from prior years.

Future research plans include repeating these analyses to compare quarterly NSDUH data from 2021 with the respective quarterly data from 2022 and gain more insight about the effects COVID-19 and data collection mode on the NSDUH outcomes.

Table 1: Results: Risk Ratios for Selected NSDUH Outcomes

<i>Outcome</i>	<i>MODE:</i> $R_M (M=1 \text{ vs. } M=0)$	<i>COVID:</i> $R_C (C=1 \text{ vs. } C=0)$	<i>MODE-COVID</i> $R_Q (M=1, C=0 \text{ vs. } M=0, C=1)$
Past Year Illicit Drug Use	1.25	1.28	0.99
Past Month Illicit Drug Use	1.28	1.37	0.96
Past Year Marijuana Use	1.28	1.33	0.98
Past Month Marijuana Use	1.33	1.44	0.94
Past Year Alcohol Use	0.98	0.96	1.03
Past Month Alcohol Use	0.98	0.96	1.03
Past Month Binge Alcohol Use	1.21	1.03	1.17
Past Year Cigarette Use	1.23	1.06	1.17
Past Month Cigarette Use	1.25	1.09	1.18
Past Year Any Mental Illness (Adult)	1.07	1.15	0.94
Past Year Suicide Attempts (Adult)	1.79	1.49	1.35

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